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Policy Guide

Evidence-Based Outreach Framework for Peace and Security Open Data Outreach

A reference framework to inform data providers' outreach policies and engagement strategies with the peacebuilding and peace & security community

Prepared by the PeaceTech Alliance (Austrian Institute of Technology), the Open Knowledge Foundation, and the Austrian Centre for Peace. This document builds on consultations conducted in July 2024 and has been developed through subsequent review and refinement.

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About this Document

This Policy Guide presents an evidence-based outreach framework for organisations that release or hold data with potential relevance for peacebuilding and broader peace and security efforts. It is designed to support data providers — including governments, intergovernmental organisations, technology companies, research institutions, and civil society actors — in improving the accessibility, usability, safety, and relevance of their data for peacebuilding actors and affected communities.

The framework is informed by primary input gathered during expert consultations and co-design sessions convened at the Austrian Forum for Peace (July 2024), bringing together practitioners from peacebuilding organisations, international organisations, the third sector, civil society, academia, and relevant technical communities.

This document does not constitute a binding standard but provides a structured reference framework that may inform:

- Organisational outreach strategies for data engagement;
- Internal data access and dissemination policies;
- Engagement campaigns directed toward the peacebuilding and peace & security community;
- Funding strategies and programme design for responsible data access initiatives.

Purpose and Intended Audience

A wide range of organisations — including those not traditionally situated within the peacebuilding domain — generate, manage, or release data that can contribute to peace and security outcomes if made accessible and usable to relevant actors.

This Policy Guide is directed at:

- Organisations that release data with potential peacebuilding or peace & security relevance;
- Providers seeking to improve data accessibility for peacebuilding practitioners;
- Institutions aiming to strengthen responsible data dissemination policies;
- Funders and policymakers developing governance frameworks for data-driven peace and security initiatives.

The framework supports these actors in aligning their data dissemination practices with the operational, ethical, and technical needs of peacebuilding practitioners.

Development Process

This framework draws on participatory policy co-design conducted at the Austrian Forum for Peace in Burgenland, Austria (July 2024), facilitated by the PeaceTech Alliance (Austrian Institute of Technology), the Open Knowledge Foundation, and the Austrian Centre for Peace. Contributors included peacebuilding experts, international organisation representatives (including the United Nations and OSCE), practitioners from the third sector, civil society, research institutions, and technology communities.

The development process identified several key barriers limiting the use of existing data for peace and security purposes, including:

- Gaps between the availability of open data and its actual use by peacebuilders;
- Barriers related to accessibility, technical complexity, and insufficient user support;
- Limited proactive outreach by data providers to peacebuilding constituencies;
- The need for responsible, ethical frameworks to address data sensitivity and conflict risk.

The resulting framework aims to address these barriers by providing an actionable reference that reflects both the operational realities of peacebuilding and responsible data management principles.

Applying the Framework

The following figure illustrates the practical steps data providers can follow to apply the Outreach Framework presented in this Policy Guide. It summarises the sequential process by which providers can identify relevant data, design effective outreach strategies, and support peacebuilding practitioners in accessing and using data for peace and security outcomes.

The process begins by identifying data holdings with potential peace and security relevance, followed by a detailed assessment of available datasets. Providers can then apply the Outreach Framework to guide their release strategy, prepare data and supporting documentation, actively engage peacebuilders as end users, and implement continuous monitoring and improvement to ensure responsible data use over time.

Figure 1: How Data Providers Can Use This Framework

Core Principles of the Outreach Framework for Peace and Security Open Data

Principle	Description
Know the Source (Transparency)	Clearly identify the publisher, source, and intended beneficiaries of the data. Transparency allows users to assess the credibility, provenance, and potential biases of datasets.
Limits of the Data (Disclosure of Limitations)	Provide clear information on data limitations, including scope, accuracy, methodology boundaries, and constraints that may affect interpretation or application.
Methodology (Documentation)	Explain the rationale for data collection, employed methodologies, tools used, and any "data invisibles" — factors not immediately apparent but crucial for understanding the dataset.
Interactive Tools (Gamification)	Develop interactive platforms and data visualisation tools that allow users to explore, analyse, and interact with datasets according to their needs and skill levels.
Contingency Plans (Data Contestation)	Establish clear mechanisms for contesting data accuracy, correcting errors, and addressing potential misuse or unintended harm from data release.
Ethical Guidelines (Ethics Framework)	Apply robust ethical standards governing data collection, processing, storage, dissemination, privacy, informed consent, and protection of vulnerable populations.
Expiration Date (Validity Period)	Assign a validity period ("use-by date") to each dataset, indicating when data should be reviewed or revalidated for ongoing relevance and accuracy.
Education Toolkits (User Guides)	Provide comprehensive training materials, tutorials, case studies, and best practice examples to support users in responsibly applying and interpreting the data.
Related Datasets (Contextual Links)	Offer references and links to complementary datasets that provide additional context, enrich analysis, and facilitate cross-referencing of information.
Bias Assessment (Bias Questionnaire)	Include structured bias assessment tools to help users evaluate potential biases in data collection, representation, and interpretation.

Software Recommendations (Open Source Tools)	Recommend open-source, freely available data analysis, visualisation, and processing tools to ensure equitable access for users regardless of institutional resources.
Sustainable Development Goals (SDG Alignment)	Clearly indicate which SDGs the data supports, using simple visual indicators (e.g. green labels) to connect data to global development frameworks.
Needs-Based Approach (Purpose-Driven Data)	Design data collection and dissemination processes that begin with the actual needs and use cases of peacebuilding practitioners and affected communities.
Do No Harm (Safety Benchmark)	Apply the "do no harm" principle systematically to minimise risks of unintended harm, conflict exacerbation, or misuse of sensitive data.
Code of Conduct (Standards Compliance)	Adopt a code of conduct for data providers that aligns with internationally recognised ethical standards and professional best practices.
Carbon Footprint (Sustainability)	Evaluate and minimise the environmental impact of data collection, processing, storage, and dissemination operations.
Positive Reinforcement (Narrative Building)	Use data to highlight positive peacebuilding outcomes, share success stories, and support constructive narratives within peace and security contexts.
Peer Review (Quality Assurance)	Implement independent peer review or validation processes prior to data release to assure data quality, reliability, and credibility.

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